

Stress Detection using Electro Dermal Activity and Face Emotion Recognition

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ABSTRACT

Stress levels in India have increased as a result of economic hardship, workplace stressors, and limited access to basic necessities and education. Chronic stress can raise the risk of mental, musculoskeletal, and cardiovascular diseases. In a similar vein, stress at work can lead to lower worker productivity and increased expenses for an organization due to employee absenteeism. The first step in addressing stress's detrimental effects on health and wellbeing during a workday is identifying stress and the events that correlate with it. These responses manifest psychologically as well as physiologically, manifesting as feelings and facial expressions. We used this

1. INTRODUCTION

Demanding jobs are a significant cause of stress in people. Situations like frequent exposure to danger, short deadlines, rigorous tasks or even repetitive tasks are some stress originators [1]. Nearly one in three workers in India report that they are affected by stress at work. Work-related stress, depression, and anxiety can result in reduced work performance and absenteeism, costing an estimated 3% to 4% of gross national product. Also, Indian research reported that are reluctance to talk openly about these issues seems to be the main difficulty for addressing psycho-social risks [2].

The formatter will need to create these components, incorporating the applicable criteria that follow. By harnessing advancements in technology, particularly in the fields of artificial intelligence and physiological monitoring, this system aims to identify and mitigate stressors proactively [3]. Combining the analysis of facial expressions, indicative of psychological distress, with the measurement of Galvanic Skin Response (GSR), a physiological marker of stress, our approach offers a holistic understanding of individuals stress levels [4]. Through the integration of a convolutional neural network (CNN) capable of recognizing facial expressions and an application for real-time data processing, this proof of concept seeks to provide a comprehensive solution for stress detection in the workplace [5].

information to create a stress detector proof of concept. utilizing a convolution neural network that can identify different facial expressions and an application that applies this model to categorize user faces in real-time images and determine whether the user is showing symptoms of stress. Real-time stress detection with a non-invasive, objective method is possible with Galvanic Skin Response (GSR). The sympathetic nervous system's activation, a defining feature of the stress response, is physiologically indicated by GSR, which measures variations in skin electrical conductance brought on by sweat gland activity.

Keywords—Stress detection, galvanic skin response, CNN

So, for different methodologies are used for stress detection. These methods are classified into Physiological Signal-Based Stress Detection and Facial Expression Analysis for Stress Detection [6]. Research on physiological signals such as heart rate variability (HRV), electroencephalography (EEG), and cortisol levels has demonstrated their effectiveness in detecting stress [7]. For instance, HRV has been shown to decrease during stress, reflecting reduced parasympathetic activity. EEG studies have identified specific brainwave patterns associated with stress, particularly in the alpha and beta bands. However, these methods often require invasive or cumbersome equipment, limiting their practical applications [8].

In Facial expressions-based approaches, they are universally recognized indicators of emotional states. Studies leveraging machine learning for facial expression analysis have shown promising results in detecting stress and other emotions [9]. Ekman's Facial Action Coding System (FACS) provides a standardized method for categorizing facial expressions, which has been instrumental in training machine learning models for emotion detection. Recent advancements in deep learning, particularly CNNs, have significantly improved the accuracy of facial recognition systems in various lighting conditions and across diverse populations [10].

Traditional methods of stress detection primarily rely on self-report questionnaires, interviews, and clinical observations. Commonly used scales include the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS)

and the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI) [11]. While these methods provide valuable insights, they are subjective and may not accurately capture real-time stress levels. Physiological methods, such as heart rate variability (HRV), cortisol level measurement, and neuroimaging techniques, offer more objective assessments but often require invasive procedures and sophisticated equipment, limiting their practicality for everyday use [12]. The escalating prevalence of stress-related conditions underscores the urgent need for advanced detection mechanisms. Conventional approaches, reliant on subjective assessments, fail to capture the nuanced physiological manifestations of stress. By harnessing the capabilities of GSR and advanced facial recognition technologies [13].

In this proposed work, aims to revolutionize stress detection, enabling timely interventions and fostering healthier environments. This study's motivation lies in bridging the gap between subjective experiences and objective measurements, ensuring precise and actionable insights into stress levels. In this article the section 2 presented the proposed methodology. The

2.METHODOLOGY

The proposed system integrates GSR data and facial recognition outputs to provide a comprehensive assessment of stress levels. Machine learning algorithms were employed to analyze the combined data, improving the accuracy and reliability of stress detection. Extensive testing was conducted in controlled environments, where participants were exposed to various stress-inducing stimuli. The system's performance was evaluated based on its ability to accurately classify stress levels. The combined approach of using EDA and facial recognition outperformed single-modality methods, demonstrating a significant increase in accuracy and reliability. Graphical representations of the data underscored the system's capability to detect stress in real-time, with minimal latency.

2.1 Stress detection using Electro Dermal Activity (EDA).

EDA measures skin conductance, which is influenced by sweat gland activity controlled by the sympathetic nervous system. Increased sweat production, a hallmark of stress response, leads to higher skin conductance. GSR sensors were used to collect EDA data, providing a physiological indicator of stress. Figure 1 shows the block diagram of Electro dermal activity-based stress detection. Here the Galvanic Skin Response (GSR) offers a promising objective and non-invasive approach for real-time stress detection. By measuring changes in skin electrical conductance due to

Experiment Preparation is explained in section 3. Results and the discussion include In Section 4 and the Section 5 draws the discussion and conclusion.

In outline, the major contributions are given below

- Development of a Dual-Modality Stress Detection System: To create an integrated system that combines EDA and facial recognition technologies for enhanced stress detection.
- Machine Learning Integration: To utilize sophisticated machine learning algorithms to improve the accuracy and reliability of stress detection.
- Real-Time Monitoring and Feedback: To enable continuous, real-time monitoring of stress levels, providing immediate feedback and potential interventions.
- Exploration of Physiological Mechanisms: To investigate the physiological underpinnings of stress responses, particularly through the lens of GSR data.

sweat gland activity, GSR provides a physiological indicator of the sympathetic nervous system's activation, a hallmark of stress response. Detecting stress and the events that correlate with stress during a workday is the first step to addressing its negative effects on health and wellbeing. These reactions are reflected not only physiologically, but also psychologically, translating into emotions and facial expressions. Based on this, we developed a proof of concept for a stress detector.

Figure1 Block diagram Electro dermal activity-based stress detection.

2.2 Stress detection based on Facial Recognition.

Facial expressions are known to reflect emotional states, including stress. A convolutional neural network (CNN) was trained to classify facial expressions indicative of stress. Real-

time images of the user's face were captured and analyzed to assess the presence of stress-related expressions.

Figure 2 Block diagram of face recognition-based stress detection.

Figure 2 shows the Block diagram of face recognition-based stress detection. The facial reactions are reflected not only physiologically, but also psychologically,

translating into emotions and facial expressions. Based on this, developed a proof of concept for a stress detector. With a convolutional neural network capable of classifying facialexpressions, and an application that uses this model to classify real-time images of the user's face and thereby assess the presence of signs of stress

Machine Learning Algorithms :

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs): CNNs are a class of deep learning algorithms particularly well-suited for image analysis tasks. In this study, a CNN was trained on a large dataset of labeled facial expressions to detect stress-related features [14]. The architecture included multiple convolutional layers, pooling layers, and fully connected layers, culminating in a softmax layer for classification. The model was trained using backpropagation and stochastic gradient descent to minimize the cross-entropy loss function [15].

Ensemble Methods:

Ensemble methods, such as random forests and gradient boosting, were explored to combine predictions from multiple models. These methods aggregate the outputs of several weak learners to improve overall accuracy and robustness. In this method, an ensemble approach was used to combine predictions from the CNN and SVM models, yielding higher accuracy in stress detection [16].

3.EXPERIMENTS PREPARATION

In this work, 120 subjects were employed to thoroughly prove the efficacy of the implemented technique. All the subjects are asked to show their face in the computer system and swape their finger in the GSR sensors.

3.1 Participant Selection and Experiment Setup:

Participants were selected based on predefined criteria, ensuring a diverse demographic representation. Each participant was subjected to controlled stress-inducing stimuli, such as time-bound tasks, public speaking scenarios, and cognitive challenges, to elicit stress responses. GSR sensors and cameras were used to collect physiological and facial data simultaneously.

Raw data from GSR sensors were filtered to remove noise and artifacts. Standard signal processing techniques, such as moving average filters and Fourier transforms, were applied to extract relevant features from the EDA signal. Forfacial

recognition, images were preprocessed using normalization techniques to ensure consistent lighting and orientation. Key facial landmarks were identified using facial detection algorithms, and the resulting features were fed into the CNN for classification.

3.2 Performance Metrics

The performance of the stress detection system was evaluated using standard metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. Confusion matrices were generated to visualize the classification performance of each model.

3.2.1 Accuracy Accuracy refers to how close a measurement is to the true or accepted value. Precision refers to how close measurements of the same item are to each other. Precision is independent of accuracy [17].

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{(\text{True positives} + \text{True Negatives})}{(\text{True positives} + \text{True Negatives} + \text{False Positives} + \text{False Negatives})}$$

The performance of the proposed face emotion detection and galvanic skin response is done using real time database. This data base contains most common types of defects.

4. Experimental Results and Analysis.

120 subjects were employed to thoroughly prove the efficacy of the implemented technique. All the subjects are asked to show their face in the computer system and swape their finger in the GSR sensors. Here only 5 subjects facial expression output and the GSR output is consider for the analysis.

Figure 5 Graphical representation of stress level, (u) Stress level of subject-1, (v) Stress level of subject-2, (w) Stress level of subject-3, (x) Stress level of subject-4, (y) Stress level of subject-

Accuracy = galvanic skin response + facial emotion detection

3.2.2 Electro Dermal Activity (EDA)

EDA is measured in micro siemens (μS), representing the skin's conductance. The formula used to calculate the skin conductance response (SCR) is:

$$\text{SCR} = \frac{\Delta C}{\Delta t} \quad \text{SCR} = \frac{\Delta C}{\Delta t}$$

where ΔC is the change in conductance, and Δt is the change in time [18].

3.2.3 Error Analysis.

An error analysis was conducted to identify common sources of misclassification. Factors such as individual differences in physiological responses, variations in facial expressions, and environmental conditions were examined. Strategies to mitigate these errors, such as personalized calibration and adaptive algorithms, were discussed. label, present them within parentheses. Do not label axes only with units. In the example, write "Magnetization (A/m)" or "Magnetization {A[m(1)]}", not just "A/m". Do not label axes with a ratio of quantities and units. For example, write "Temperature (K)", not "Temperature/K" [19].

5.

Figure 3a Detection results of face, (a-d) Detection results of face of the subject-1, (e-h) Detection results of face of the subject-2.

Figure 3b Detection results of face, (i-l) Detection results of face of the subject-3, (m-p) Detection results of face of the subject 4, (q-t) Detection results of face of the subject-5.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The results were compared against baseline models and traditional stress detection methods. The dual-modality approach demonstrated superior performance, with significant improvements in accuracy and real-time detection. The dual-modality approach to stress detection offers a significant advancement over traditional methods. The integration of physiological and behavioral indicators provides a holistic view of an individual's stress levels. Machine learning algorithms play a crucial role in refining the system's accuracy, addressing challenges such as individual variability in stress responses. Future work will focus on expanding the dataset, improving algorithm robustness, and exploring additional physiological

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Sl.No	Name	GSR Output	Result
1.	Alan	197	Not Stressed
2.	Dinesh Kumar	233	Not Stressed
3.	obied	506	Stressed
4.	kathir	496	Stressed
5	Harish	350	Neutral

Table 1 Stress level obtained by GS signals to further enhance the system's efficacy.

5.1 CONCLUSION

This Research work presents a comprehensive approach to stress detection, integrating EDA and facial recognition technologies to provide a robust, non-invasive solution. The dual-modality system demonstrates significant improvements in accuracy and real-time detection capabilities compared to traditional methods. The potential applications of this technology are vast, offering valuable insights and interventions in various settings, from workplaces to healthcare and education. Future developments will focus on refining the system's accuracy, expanding its applicability, and addressing ethical considerations related to data privacy and user consent.

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